

Autonomous Wireless Sensor System Design for Structural Health Monitoring Application

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Abstract—Infrastructures such as roads, railway tracks, buildings, bridges and tunnels etc. suffer from degradation over a period of time. Phenomena such as ageing, hazards and natural disasters significantly affect the structure’s sustainability. Structures require timely monitoring and maintenance to assure long term structural integrity, health and safety. Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) helps in early damage detection and improvement in the reliability of structures by enabling retrofitting of wireless sensors to capture data to help detecting potential failures. In this work, an innovative design concept for an autonomous system based on Self-repairing Spiking Astrocyte Neural Networks (SANNs) with Self-powered Sensor Nodes has been described. SANNs offer an energy efficient computing approach with the capability to mimic the self-repairing principles of the human brain for highly-reliable information processing. It is adept to tolerating failures by adapting the network topology and re-learning the input-output mapping, whereby it can bypass a significant number of non-operational nodes whilst still maintaining an adequate SHM sensory infrastructure. The design also provides an opportunity to reduce the power consumption of the wireless sensor by implementing the model as a Big-little architecture. This enables extremely low energy always-on ‘little’ sensor nodes (SN) to operate in combination with ‘big’ on-demand, neuromorphic anomaly detectors (NAD). Energy harvesting through vibrational or solar ambient energies can help supply sufficient power for the sensor node to maintain an ‘always-on’ state, while periodic analysis of sensor output data exceeding a threshold-level could help in anomalies detection for self-repairing algorithms. A pulsed mode with on-time and event-based duty cycle management helps in minimizing the average power consumption of sensor nodes. The NAD, powered typically by solar energy harvesting, is activated on threshold attainment and analyses the incoming data for further anomalies.

Index Terms—Spiking Neural Networks, Energy harvesting, structural health monitoring, autonomous nodes

I. INTRODUCTION

Structural health monitoring is a tool for detecting degradation in aerospace, civil, and mechanical infrastructures. Extreme stresses can create cracks and deformation at critical structural places, leading to partial or complete collapse, as shown in the Surfside building disaster in 2021 [2] and the Malahide estuary viaduct collapse in 2009 [3]. As a result, structural health monitoring (SHM) is required on a regular basis to ensure the structure’s health and endurance. It is crucial to detect/quantify the extent of damage early on and assess the existing structural health and reliability for safe

use and even predict probable failures and intervene. In order to accomplish this, technology is being developed to replace qualitative visual inspections and time-based maintenance processes with more quantitative and repeatable procedures. Sensors are employed to detect structural degradation, and many sensors, such as accelerometers, strain and displacement gauges are mounted to structures at important places to collect structural data. The current SHM system design lacks a low-energy consumption, highly reliable, and self-contained framework for damage categorization based on a continuous data record. Signal processing is used to extract, identify, and classify essential aspects that are utilized to measure structure health. Traditional classification methods, such as k-mean clustering, can result in incorrect categorization due to the sensitivity of the retrieved data features [4]. Traditional Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) show promise as they learn to classify data in the same way that the human brain works [5]. ANNs can automatically extract features from data using multiple categorization methods for different structures and sensor types, such as measuring mechanical/environmental qualities [6]. However, due to their inefficient power needs, these present ANN techniques are not suited for wireless SHM systems. The only financially and logistically viable solution for many structures, particularly those already erected, is to retrofit wireless sensor nodes (WSNs). This is especially difficult for large-scale deployments (> 100 sensors) in isolated or difficult-to-reach locations where wiring and a stable power source are unattainable. These solutions are ugly, unreliable, and difficult to use due to their short battery life. Typical commercial solutions use 10s to 100s of milli-watts of power, resulting in a battery life of about 5 years. One of the main goals is to lower the power consumption to under $100 \mu\text{W}$, allowing for power autonomy by harvesting ambient energy such as light, heat, or vibrations in or near the building. It has been illustrated in [1] that if power consumption can be reduced to these levels, power autonomy and battery life of 50 years can be achieved; see Fig. I. This necessitates not only require careful selection but also integration of hardware components to reduce power consumption. The use of algorithms that dynamically change network and device configurations to reduce power consumption is one of the major requirements for effective SHM. Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) is the third

Fig. 1. Sweet Spot for Energy Harvesting [1]

generation of neural network models, providing an alternative (neuromorphic) and significantly more energy-efficient event-based computing technique, with a lower hardware overhead than ANNs [7], [8]. Such neuromorphic systems use three orders of magnitude less energy than ANNs; for example, showing extreme low-energy budgets of 1.12 to 1.7 μJ per inference/classification [9]. Furthermore, recent developments in our understanding of glial cells, such as the astrocyte, have demonstrated a self-repairing capability employing a novel learning rule with regulated connections between astrocytes and neurons in new spiking neural-astrocyte networks [10]. This capability bridges the gap between high-reliability and low-energy computation paradigms. At a high level, the adoption of a new AI approach (SANN) has the potential to reduce power consumption by 2-3 orders of magnitude, allowing for the achievement of the energy harvesting sweet spot (and power autonomy), as well as a self-repairing capability that allows for the bypassing of a significant number of non-operational WSNs, up to 15% in order to maintain reliable SHM.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system design is based on a Big-little micro-architecture. In this system, tasks are allocated to different processors depending on their performance and power requirements. An implementation is shown in Fig 2. The little processor acts as a sensor node which receives data from connected sensors. This little processor performs threshold detection, and transfers the analysed data to the bigger processor. The bigger processor contains the SANNs which

analyses the periodically received data from little processor for detection of anomalies. The self-repairing implementation helps in detection of non-functional sensor nodes through re-learning the input-output mapping, via undamaged pathways. This implementation provides a highly-reliable, low-energy compute paradigm. The big processor, on the basis of analysed data, would then instruct the little processor to increase or decrease sensing and transmission intervals. This dynamic switching of intervals would reduce the overall power consumption and improve the system performance. The big processor also has a functionality to store data at the cloud for further investigation to improve overall system performance. According to the application, average power consumption at the sensor level is governed by in the pulsed mode with on-time and duty cycle management. Hence, the on-demand NAD can be adjusted dynamically through the SANNs. The NAD is activated on threshold attainment as it starts to process the incoming data for anomalies. To achieve better reliability, a neuromorphic hardware is implemented with SANNs which adapts to hardware failure through re-mapping computations providing a fault-free resources. Hence, the repairing capability provides less degrade in operation on increasing failures [10]. The presence of an autonomous learning mechanism that combines adaptive astrocytes in SANNs helps in better interaction between spiking neurons. Events exceeding threshold are transmitted from the SN to NAD. Anomalies detected are communicated to a cloud-gateway for intervention. In a 100 SNs, every 10 SNs can feed a NAD. The malfunctioning NAD adapts to the SANNs structure for repairing the synapse. For failing SNs, the NAD re-routes the data path to the remaining

Fig. 2. Big-little Concept Architecture

Fig. 3. a. Total power consumption by different processor under similar conditions b. Total power consumption by STM L0 with sensing interval ranging from 60 sec to 3600 sec

healthy SNs. The key towards an autonomous system forms in selection of a little processor capable of performing the functionality in lower power. The low power capability allows the SN to maintain the 'always-on' state as well as help in powering it through energy harvesting. The processing requirements of the SN is kept light and data transeving is kept local between SN & NADs to minimize energy consumption & render use of small PV panels, to self -power the SN. In general, SHM detects defects through changes in vibration of the structure which could form a source of energy harvesting for the sensor node. Determining the correct processor for the implementation plays a key role in reduction of power consumed.

III. EXPECTED RESULTS

In order to select the optimum processor, a mathematical tool is developed that helps to determine the power consumed by the processor while performing various tasks. This was done as an EU EnABLES transnational access feasibility study, a collaboration between Tyndall National Institute & Ulster University. The power consumption is divided into three categories i.e. sensing power, active power and sleep power. Sensing power refers to the approximate power required by the processor to operate the sensors to sense a specific characteristic like vibration, strain etc. Active power is a summation of processing and transmission power required by the processor. In most cases, active power is the highest power consumed

by the processor. When the processor is neither active nor sensing it is in sleep mode. Sleep power is consumed for a larger time duration as compared to the other two operation modes. As the timing interval tends to increase the majority of power is consumed by the processor in sleep mode compared to the other modes. A comparison of state of the art low power processor power consumption with respect to different timing intervals is shown in Fig. 3a. Low power processors from some leading manufacturers for IoT applications are analysed. So far the STM L0 series processor has the least power consumption under similar conditions as compared to the other micro-processors.

As the sensing time interval is varied, sleep power becomes the principal contributor of the total power consumption. Fig. 3b shows the reduction of total power consumption with increasing sensing intervals for the STM L0 processor. A tool such as that developed will give critical guidance into selecting an optimal processor as well as giving an up-front insight into the trade-off between sensing intervals & power consumption.

IV. CONCLUSION

An autonomous system design of an IoT network for structural health monitoring has been shown in this work. A Big-little architecture providing efficient power consumption for the wireless sensors has also been discussed. The network consists of extremely low energy always-on ‘little’ sensor nodes to operate in combination with ‘big’ on-demand, neuromorphic anomaly detectors. The choice of micro-processor for the always-on ‘little’ sensor node plays a crucial role in determining its total power consumption. Different micro-processor’s total power consumptions under similar working conditions are compared. Based on the micro-controller units (MCU) investigated, STM L0 has the lowest power consumption of 20 μ W for a 900 ns sensing interval. Hence, Due to its low power consumption it can be easily powered by vibrational or solar energy harvesting. Further study on the design would potentially develop an autonomous system which would help in providing early damage detection as well as in improving structural health and endurance. Simulation models, are a critical enabler to give insight into optimal MCU selection & system level power consumption to investigate, self-powering via energy harvesting.

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